

THE EFFECT OF PLY THICKNESS ON THE DAMAGE MECHANISMS IN NOTCHED COMPOSITES

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Abstract

The effect of ply thickness on the damage mechanisms in notched composites in order was investigated using progressive failure analysis (PFA) methodology. For thicker ply laminates, higher thermal residual stresses lead to accelerating matrix cracking, delamination, splitting damage and failure type transits from brittle or pull-out to delamination.

Keywords: *Damage mechanism; PFA; Failure mode; Delamination*

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) composites have been widely used for structural applications due to their high strength, low weight, ability to manufacture complex geometries and other factors. The notched strength and failure modes are important topics in composite structures and notched strength depends on the failure mode.

The notched behavior of composite materials has been investigated over the past 30 years, both experimentally and numerically. The failure modes of open hole tensile tests were given by Green[1] and were identified to brittle, pull-out and delamination. The failure modes of open hole compressive tests were given by Wisnom[2], similar to those identified in tension. The effect of stacking sequence and hole diameter on notched strength were investigated by Lagace et al.[3], who found that hole diameter has a significant effect on the fracture of $[0/90_2]_s$ laminates. The fracture mode changes from matrix-dominated to fiber-dominated with the increasing hole diameter. The stress redistribution in open hole composite laminates due to damage accumulation was reported by Iarve et al.[4], Iarve found that the fiber direction stress relaxes at the hole edge due to matrix cracking. The size effect on the strength of open-hole tension and compression laminates was investigated by Wisnom and Hallett[2], they found that both strength and failure mechanisms changing with the laminates size. Wisnom et al.[5] found that delamination has a crucial role in the in-plane strength, failure mechanism and hole size effect in open hole tension of quasi-isotropic laminates, and can lead to premature failure, especially for small holes and thick ply blocks. Vaidya et al. [6] investigated the ply block thickness effect on notched strength of cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates. The amount of delamination increases with the ply thickness, and

for quasi-isotropic specimens the failure mode switched from fibre failure to delamination when four plies were blocked together.

Results of several different series of open hole tension tests on quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 laminates with different ply thicknesses were summarized in reference [1]. The objective of this paper was to investigate the ply thickness effect on the damage mechanism in the notched composites by progressive failure methodology.

2 Experiment

The experimental results published by Green et. al.[1] covered an extensive program investigating the extent of the ply thickness effect on damage mechanisms in open hole specimens and unnotched specimens. The open hole specimens were selected to validate the effectiveness of the progressive failure analysis (PFA) methodology used in the study and investigate the ply thickness effect on damage mechanisms in notched composites. Quasi-isotropic $[45_n/90_n/-45_n/0_n]_s$ (the subscripts n refers to the number of plies for which values of 1,2,4 or 8 were chosen to represent different ply thicknesses) specimens containing a circular hole were tested in tension. The material used was IM7/8552, an unidirectional (UD) carbon-fiber/epoxy pre-preg system supplied by Hexcel, with a nominal ply thickness of 0.125 mm. A schematic diagram of the specimen tested was presented in Figure 1. The dimension of the specimen, such as the width and length, were dependent on the diameter of the hole. Specimens and test results were summarized in Table 1. Fig 2 shows the effect of ply thickness on the open-hole tension results for the specimens with different diameter holes. The unnotched thicker ply specimen's strength is significantly lower than that of thinner specimen (drops about 21.6% in from 0.125mm to 0.25mm, 30% in from 0.25mm to 0.5mm, 30% in from 0.5mm to 1.0mm), and the

failure type changes from pull-out to delamination . The notched specimens show the same trend with the unnotched specimen.

Fig. 1.Schematic diagram of specimens[1]

Fig.2. experiment results

Table. 1. Experimental strength and failure type [1]

Ply thickness (mm)	Hole Sizes (mm)	Failure strength (MPa)	Failure type
0.125	0	842	Pull-out
0.125	3.175	570	Pull-out
0.25	0	660	Pull-out
0.25	3.175	396	Delamination
0.25	6.35	498	Pull-out
0.5	0	458	Delamination
0.5	3.175	275	Delamination
0.5	6.35	285	Delamination
0.5	12.7	362	Delamination
0.5	25.4	417	Delamination
1.0	0	321	Delamination
1.0	3.175	202	Delamination
1.0	25.4	232	Delamination

3 Model

In order to capture the effect of ply thickness on the damage mechanisms in notched composites, both

intra-laminar and inter-laminar damage models were considered in the finite element model based on the PFA methodology. The PFA methodology was implemented using user defined field (VUSDFLD) subroutine and cohesive element in the ABAQUS/Explicit nonlinear finite element code [7].

3.1 intra-laminar damage model

The fiber damage and matrix damage in a lamina were detected by Hashin-Rotem unidirectional failure criteria[8,9]. The failure criteria are expressed in terms of the in-plane stresses and strengths. Damage modes are predicted by the following expressions:

Fiber damage ($d_f = 0$):

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t} \right) \geq 1.0, \sigma_{11} > 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_c} \right) \geq 1.0, \sigma_{11} < 0$$

Matrix damage ($d_m = 0$):

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 \geq 1.0, \sigma_{22} > 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{12}}{S_{12}} \right)^2 \geq 1.0, \sigma_{22} < 0$$

Once damage occurs, the corresponding terms in the constitutive matrix are instantaneously degraded to zero using damage parameters. The stress-strain relationship with the damage parameters for a 2-D orthotropic material can be written as the following expressions:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)Q_{11} & d_0Q_{12} & 0 \\ d_0Q_{12} & d_0Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & d_0Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Where

$$d_0 = (1-d_f)(1-d_m)$$

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_1}{(1-d_0\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}$$

$$Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{12}E_2}{(1-d_0\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}$$

$$Q_{22} = \frac{E_2}{(1-d_0\nu_{12}\nu_{21})}$$

$$Q_{66} = G_{12}$$

3.2 inter-laminar damage model

Cohesive elements were placed at the interface between the plies to simulate the initiation and progression of inter-laminar damage, or delamination. The onset of delamination was detected based on the inter-laminar quadratic nominal stress criterion and the delamination growth was based on a critical fracture energy criterion. A detailed explanation of the cohesive model could be found in Refs.10-11. The cohesive layer parameters such as element size, stiffness and the interfacial strengths of the interface between the plies were determined by the guidelines presented in Ref. 12. The stiffness of the cohesive layer in the mode-I direction is defined by the following equation in Ref.12

$$K_{mn} = \frac{\alpha E_3}{t} \quad (4)$$

Where α is a parameter much larger than 1. However, large values of the cohesive stiffness may cause numerical problems. A value of α equal to 50 was recommended in Ref.12 and was used in this study to determine the stiffness of cohesive layer. In calculating the stiffness in the shear directions, E_3 is replaced with $2G_{12}$ and $2G_{23}$, respectively.

3.3 finite element model

Three-dimensional (3D) finite element models of nine specimen configurations according to table 1 were developed to simulate the coupled inter- and intra laminar damage progression. Half of the specimens were modeled due to their symmetry in the thickness direction. The thickness of each model was divided into four ply sections with a cohesive layer of zero thickness between each of them. The ply sections were discretized in the in-plane directions using 8-node continuum shell reduced integration element (SC8R). The cohesive layers were modeled using a zero thickness 8-node cohesive element known as COH3D8. The stiffnesses and strengths of COH3D8 were determined by the guidelines presented in Ref.12 according to the element sizes.

3.4 results and discussions

The modeling results were summarized in Table 2 and compared with the test results. The modeling results show that the notched strength decreasing with increasing the ply thickness and the failure type changing from pull-out to delamination, which is the same with the test results. Comparing the modeling

results with the experiment results, we can conclude that the model could be used to investigate the effect of ply thickness on the damage mechanisms of open hole tensile specimens.

Fig 3 show the maximum thermal stresses in the transverse direction and shear stress in the hole edge of different specimens. It can be concluded that thermal stresses during the curing process of the specimen increasing with the ply thickness and matrix cracks will be introduced by the thermal stresses. This is validated by Fig 4 in Ref 13. The thicker ply would also accelerate the splitting damage as shown by Fig 5. As a result of the matrix crack and split damage, delamination would increase with the ply thickness, as shown by Fig 6.

Table. 2. Modeling strength and failure type

Ply thickness (mm)	Hole Sizes (mm)	Failure strength (MPa)	Error (%)	Failure type
0.125	3.175	534	-6.3	Pull-out
0.25	3.175	442	11.6	Delamination
0.25	6.35	485	-2.6	Pull-out
0.5	3.175	336	22.2	Delamination
0.5	6.35	334	17.2	Delamination
0.5	12.7	377	4.1	Delamination
0.5	25.4	414	-0.7	Delamination
1.0	3.175	192	-5.0	Delamination
1.0	25.4	226	-2.6	Delamination

Fig.3. max thermal stresses in the hole edge of models.

Fig.4. X-ray radiograph of IM7/8552[45/90/-45/90]s with ply thickness equal to 1mm, Extensive matrix cracking due to thermal stresses is shown[13].

(a) Ply thickness=0.125mm, hole=3.175mm

(b) Ply thickness=1.0mm, hole=3.175mm

Fig.5. splitting damage in 0° ply of models (gray represent damage)

(1) 45/0 interface

(2) 90/-45 interface

(3) -45/0 interface

(a) Ply thickness=0.125mm, hole=3.175mm

(1) 45/90 interface

(2) 90/-45 interface

(3) -45/0 interface

(b) Ply thickness=1.0mm,hole=3.175mm

Fig. 6. delamination of models at the final failure(gray represent damage)

4 Conclusion

The PFA methodology with intra-and inter-laminar damage model had been presented. Failure strengths and failure types in $[45_n/90_n/-45_n/0_n]_s$ laminates with a central circular hole in tensile load were predicted and compared with published test results. The PFA methodology was able to accurately predict the failure strength and failure type of $[45_n/90_n/-45_n/0_n]_s$ laminates.

Delamination at the hole edge and free edge was the significant damage mechanism in the thick ply laminates. For thicker ply laminates, higher thermal residual stress and shear stress are observed, thus leading to accelerating matrix cracking and splitting damage. The matrix crack and split damage will lead to delamination and failure type transits from brittle or pull-out to delamination.

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